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**Economic Impact of a Maternal *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Vaccine:
Estimates for 107 Low- and Middle-Income Countries**

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Abstract

Sepsis is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality among newborns in low- and middle-income countries, and its treatment is further complicated by high rates of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) to current antibiotics. We assessed the economic impact of a proposed maternal vaccine to protect neonates against sepsis caused by *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 107 low- and middle-income countries. We estimated vaccine-avertable medical expenditures, vaccine-avertable productivity losses due to caregiver absenteeism from work, and vaccine-avertable monetized disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) using a country-specific value of statistical life-year estimate. Implementing a maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine could avert US\$6.9 billion (95% CI: 5.6-8.3) in monetized DALYs annually across 107 countries. Countries in the African region displayed the highest median vaccine-avertable medical costs and productivity losses per capita associated with resistance to first- and second-line treatments compared to other regions. Low-income countries were disproportionately impacted by the increased medical expenditures associated with AMR, with the median price of third-line antibiotic treatment in these countries being 23.9 days of income. Our estimates indicate that a maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine could significantly reduce the societal economic burden and catastrophic health expenditures for families affected by neonatal sepsis and AMR in low- and middle-income countries.

Introduction

Sepsis is a substantial driver of neonatal morbidity and mortality, causing 1.3–3.9 million neonatal cases and 400–700 thousand deaths annually around the globe (1). The risk of severe long-term sequelae associated with neonatal sepsis is high, impacting quality of life in the future (2). *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is the leading cause of culture-confirmed neonatal sepsis in low- and middle-income countries (3), and a maternal vaccine is a promising way of reducing the overall neonatal sepsis burden (4). Such a vaccine would be administered to expectant mothers, thereby conferring protective antibodies to the newborn.

By preventing infections and reducing disease severity, a vaccine would limit the transmission of susceptible and drug-resistant strains, thereby supporting antimicrobial stewardship efforts to reduce antibiotic use, a primary driver of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (5). AMR is a pressing global health challenge that exacerbates the burden of neonatal sepsis: up to 81% of infections have been reported to be resistant to last-resort carbapenem antibiotics in high-burden countries (6). Data from the NeoOBS study in 11 countries showed that despite receiving empiric antibiotic treatment, an estimated 18% of neonates died because of an infection associated with AMR (7).

Several studies have quantified the impact of individual vaccines on AMR mitigation (8–11), and most recently, the *Lancet* Series on Sustainable Access to Effective Antibiotics estimated that routine childhood immunization with high-priority vaccines could prevent 181,500 AMR-associated deaths annually in low- and middle-income countries (12). Despite their role in reducing the incidence of infectious diseases and against a backdrop of increasing drug resistance, vaccine coverage is currently stagnating and backsliding globally, primarily due to vaccine hesitancy and reductions in global health funding (13). Middle-income countries not eligible for Gavi support or those transitioning out of Gavi support are particularly vulnerable to increases in vaccine-preventable diseases (14). A better understanding of the health and economic benefits of vaccines can help countries prioritize vaccines with the most significant impact on public health. However, until recently, the broader benefits of preventing drug-resistant infections have not been considered in vaccine value assessments (15).

AMR exacerbates the infectious disease burden from a societal and economic perspective. For instance, managing resistant infections typically requires longer hospital stays and incurs higher medical costs (16,17). In some contexts, advanced antibiotic treatments may not be accessible or affordable (18). Nearly 17% of all deaths attributable to AMR occur in children under 5 years old (19), underscoring the need to control AMR to mitigate devastating societal impacts and long-term economic losses.

The research quantifying vaccine-preventable economic costs of AMR is sparse, though previous studies have addressed bacterial pathogens with significant drug resistance. A cost-effectiveness analysis for the WHO prequalified typhoid conjugate vaccine (TCV) in 54 Gavi-eligible countries estimated that TCV is

likely cost-effective in countries with a typhoid incidence rate greater than 300 per 100,000 persons (20). Enhanced uptake of pneumococcal conjugate vaccines in China could prevent an estimated \$371-586 million in direct and indirect costs over five years (21). Other economic analyses have demonstrated the cost-effectiveness of improved tuberculosis vaccination (such as that from the M72/AS01_E vaccine in phase III clinical trials) in South Africa and India (22,23). However, for many currently available and new vaccines in development, these estimates are either missing or do not include the societal costs associated with the AMR burden.

Here, we provide the first global economic evaluation of a proposed *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine. We build on previous modeling estimates of the health burden avertable by a hypothetical maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine (10) to present national estimates of economic impact through monetized disability-adjusted life years (DALYs), direct medical expenditures, and productivity losses in 107 low- and middle-income countries. We estimate the vaccine-avertable economic burden of *K. pneumoniae* resistant to common antibiotic treatments. Additionally, we evaluate catastrophic expenditures that exceed a certain threshold of household income, forcing a household to sacrifice basic needs or become indebted (24).

Methods

Study overview

To estimate the economic impact of a potential *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine in 107 low- and middle-income countries, we converted previously published estimates of the vaccine's effect on the annual health burden of *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis into monetized values. We estimated the annual avertable monetized DALYs, avertable medical expenditures, and avertable productivity losses that could be achieved through a vaccination campaign. These metrics have been used in a prior economic evaluation of a Lassa virus vaccine rollout (25). A flowchart illustrating the concept of the economic impact model is shown in **Figure 1**.

We provide all estimates for vaccine efficacy (VE) scenarios of 70% in the Main Text and 50% in the supplementary materials. From the avertable medical expenditures, we also calculate vaccine-avertable catastrophic expenditures. In addition to estimating the vaccine-avertable economic burden metrics for all *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis cases, we provide separate estimates that account for resistance to antibiotics to treat neonatal sepsis: ampicillin/gentamicin (first-line), ceftazidime (second-line), and meropenem (third-line). Ampicillin and gentamicin are recommended as first-line empirical treatments for serious bacterial infections, including neonatal sepsis (26). However, *K. pneumoniae* is intrinsically resistant to ampicillin (26–29); therefore, we use resistance rates for gentamicin only, but include antibiotic prices for both drugs in our calculations pertaining to first-line treatments.(10)

Our analysis provides estimates for 107 countries from various World Health Organization (WHO) regions (African region [AFR] $n = 40$, region of the Americas [AMR] $n = 19$, Eastern Mediterranean region [EMR] $n = 15$, European region [EUR] $n = 15$, South-East Asia region [SEAR] $n = 10$, and Western-Pacific region [WPR] $n = 8$) and World Bank income group classifications (low income [LIC] $n = 23$, lower-middle income [LMIC] $n = 41$, and upper-middle income [UMIC] $n = 43$) (Supplementary **Table S1**). Income classifications were drawn from the World Bank as of 2024 (30). While 2021 was chosen as the base year for all economic inputs as it is the most recently applicable year to the epidemiological estimates, we present all results in 2024 US\$, adjusted for inflation.

AMR-associated avertable cases and deaths of neonatal sepsis

We obtained annual estimates (median and 95% Bayesian Credible intervals [CrI], which represent uncertainty in estimation) of avertable cases and deaths from all *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis in the 107 countries of interest from the supplementary materials of a prior study that assumed vaccine coverage equivalent to that of the maternal tetanus vaccine and utilized neonatal sepsis mortality data from 18 countries spanning 2015 to 2020 (10). Additionally, we obtained the annual avertable deaths (median and 95% CrIs) associated with resistance to gentamicin, ceftazidime, and meropenem, as well as the fraction of overall cases associated with each of those resistance types in each WHO region (10).

The study that provided these estimates modeled the antimicrobial susceptibility testing line-list data from two global neonatal mortality studies in a Bayesian framework meant to capture uncertainty in the surveillance process and produce conservative estimates of resistance that accounted for within-country heterogeneity (10). We multiplied these fractions by the overall avertable case estimates to obtain the avertable cases by resistance type. We generated Gamma distributions for the overall case counts and the fraction associated with each type of resistance and estimated uncertainty using 100,000 Monte Carlo simulations.

Avertable monetized DALYs

We used avertable cases and deaths to calculate avertable DALYs, which we then monetized utilizing the value of statistical life-year (VSLY) approach. DALYs, a health outcome, are calculated as the sum of years of life lost (YLL) and years of life lived with disability (YLD) (**Equation 1**).

$$DALYs = YLLs + YLDs \quad (1)$$

Where YLLs are calculated as the number of deaths multiplied by the number of life years lost discounted to the present, and YLDs are calculated as the number of cases that did not result in death multiplied by the number of life years lived with a disability. We used the life expectancy (LE) at birth for the number of life years lost or lived with disability. For each case, we weighted these years by the prevalence of long-term sequelae and relevant disability weights (DW) for each associated condition used in the 2021 Global Burden of Disease study (**Equation 2** and Supplementary **Text S1**) (31).

$$YLD_{percase} = LE \times \sum_j prevalence_j \times DW_j \quad (2)$$

where j represents the different long-term sequelae associated with neonatal sepsis.

The VSLY approach entails calculating the value of a statistical life (VSL) in each country as shown in **Equation 3** (32). The VSL in each country c is calculated by indexing the VSL in the United States to the country of interest using gross national income (GNI) per capita (GNIpc).

$$VSL_c = VSL_{USA} (GNIpc_c / GNIpc_{USA})^\epsilon \quad (3)$$

The elasticity (ϵ) of VSL represents the change in VSL value associated with a one percent change in real income (32). We assumed $\epsilon = 1.5$ as all countries in the analysis are low- and middle-income in the main results (32), and provided a sensitivity analysis for levels $\epsilon = 1.3$ to $\epsilon = 1.7$ in the supplement. For the United States, we assumed a VSL of 11.8 million US\$ when using 2021 as the base year, as indicated by the US Department of Transportation (33). If the resulting VSL was less than 20 times the country's 2021

GNI per capita, we used the 20 times GNI per capita threshold instead (32). We chose 2021 as the base year for demographic and economic variables because the epidemiological inputs incorporated data up through 2020.

We calculated VSLY by dividing the VSL by life expectancy at birth. We discounted these future losses to present value as per the continuous equation by Rushby and Hanson (34). In the main results we used a discount rate in the main results of three percent, a value commonly used in health economic analyses (35). In the supplement, we also provided a sensitivity analysis using rates of four and five percent, as recent work has shown that perhaps higher discount rates may be appropriate in low- and middle-income countries (35). We then estimated monetized avertable DALYs in country c by multiplying VSLY in that country with the avertable DALYs (**Equation 4**).

$$\text{monetizedDALY}_{S_c} = \text{DALY}_{S_c} \times \text{VSLY}_c \quad (4)$$

Avertable medical expenditures

To calculate the AMR-associated medical expenditures that are avertable by the *K. pneumoniae* vaccine for a country, we multiplied the number of avertable cases in the country by the cost per case, defined as the sum of the expenses for antibiotic treatment and hospital stay (**Equation 5**).

$$ME_c = a_c + h_c \times d \quad (5)$$

Where ME_c represents the medical expenditures for a single case of *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis in country c , a represents the cost of antibiotics for one case in country c , h represents the cost of a single night of hospital stay in country c , and d represents the days spent in the hospital for neonatal sepsis, which we varied based on drug resistance profile.

We assumed that the cost of antibiotic treatment varies according to the *K. pneumoniae* resistance profile. For our estimates, we assumed that all cases incur the expense of first-line antibiotic treatments, ampicillin and gentamicin; cases that are resistant to the first-line treatment incur the additional cost of second-line treatment, ceftriaxone (a third-generation cephalosporin like ceftazidime which was substituted due to data availability); and cases resistant to second-line treatment incur the additional cost of the third-line treatment, meropenem (36,37). We lacked data for the prevalence of multidrug resistance in all regions; therefore, for estimates involving all cases, we limited medical expenditures to the cost of first-line treatment. We assumed that antibiotic costs vary by geographic region (Supplementary **Text S1**). We estimated the length of hospital stay through a meta-analysis (Supplementary **Text S1**). We used the inpatient cost at a primary care facility from the WHO CHOosing Interventions that are Cost-Effective (CHOICE) initiative for the hospital cost per day (Supplementary **Text S1**) (38).

Using country-level estimates of the percent of out-of-pocket (OOP) medical expenditures from the WHO's Global Health Expenditure Database (39), we estimated the division of medical costs between patients and providers. We then follow the general approach from Smith and colleagues to calculate catastrophic expenditures (40). Briefly, the avertable expenditures are considered catastrophic in a country if the OOP medical treatment costs for a case exceed a certain percentage of annual income (41), which we measured by GNI per capita. We present results for 10% and 25% thresholds.

Avertable productivity loss

We calculated avertable productivity loss for each country and type of resistance as the productivity losses accrued due to caregiver absenteeism from work. We assumed that for each neonatal case, at least one parent serves as the child's caregiver and takes time off work to be at the hospital for the duration of treatment. The income loss avertable through vaccination is calculated as income per day (see **Table 1**) multiplied by the number of days spent in the hospital.

Data and code availability

Uncertainty in parameter inputs was propagated through Monte Carlo simulations (100,000 simulations) on all calculations, sampling from parameter distributions as indicated in **Table 1** and **Supplementary Text S1**. All economic outputs in 2021 US\$ were converted to 2024 US\$ by multiplying by the cumulative inflation rate between the years of 15.8% (42). Country-level results are presented as the mean and 95% confidence interval (CI), in 2024 US\$, as indicated. Results by region and income group are presented as the median and interquartile range (IQR) of country-level means, as indicated.

The analysis was completed using R version 4.4.0. Model inputs, parameters and their sources are provided in **Table 1**. Where detailed calculations or meta-analyses were required, further explanation is given in **Supplementary Text S1**. Spreadsheets of all inputs and parameters, as well as the R code files necessary to replicate the analysis, figures, and tables in this paper, are available on GitHub:

<https://github.com/iimpalli/kpneumo-vaccine-economic-estimates>.

Results

Vaccine-avertable monetized DALYs

The overall annual avertable monetized DALYs from a *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine, with coverage equivalent to that of the maternal tetanus vaccine and 70% vaccine efficacy across 107 countries, was 6.9 billion (95% CI: 5.6-8.3) in 2024 US\$ (denoted \$ hereafter). The avertable monetized DALYs across countries ranged from \$0.3 million (North Macedonia) to \$1.4 billion (India). The top five countries with the highest avertable monetized DALYs were India with \$1.4 billion (95% CI 1.2-1.7), China with \$1.1 billion (0.9-1.3), Nigeria with \$0.6 billion (0.5-0.7), Indonesia with \$0.4 billion (0.3-0.4), and Mexico with \$0.3 billion (0.3-0.4) (**Table S2**). A similar ranking of countries was observed for the alternative VE scenario of 50% (**Table S3**). The avertable DALYs from the maternal vaccine reflect both YLD and YLL, with an average YLD-to-YLL ratio of 1.20 (range: 1.17-1.21). Estimates of the avertable YLD and YLL in each country are provided in **Table S4**.

Across the 107 countries, the mean avertable monetized DALYs per capita was \$1.17, with a median of \$0.85. The country with the highest avertable monetized DALYs per capita was Botswana with \$7.08 (95% CI: 5.76-8.52), followed by Gabon with \$5.46 (4.45-6.57), the Dominican Republic with \$5.36 (4.36-6.44), Turkmenistan with \$3.86 (3.14-4.64), and Equatorial Guinea with \$3.61 (2.94-4.35) (**Figure 2A** and **Table S5**). Country-level benefits of the vaccine as measured in monetized DALYs were greatest in the region of the Americas with a median of \$1.11 (IQR: 0.73-1.51) followed by the WHO African region, with a median of \$1.00 (IQR: 0.59-1.68) (**Figure 2B**).

Vaccine-avertable economic burden associated with AMR

The total avertable monetized DALYs associated with resistance to antibiotics were greatest for resistance to first-line antibiotic treatment, totaling \$4.3 billion (95% CI: 3.2-5.6) across 107 countries (**Table 2**). Total vaccine-avertable medical expenditures and productivity loss from caregiver absenteeism from work due to *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis cases resistant to first-line treatment were also the highest among all types of resistance, at \$73.1 million (26.6-153.8) and \$19.2 million (12.6-27.4), respectively (**Table 2**). The countries that had the largest combined avertable medical expenditures and productivity losses associated with first-line treatment resistance were India at \$15.6 million (6.9-29.6), Nigeria at \$9.8 million (4.8-17.9), and Iran at \$9.3 million (2.7-21.1) (**Table S5**). A similar ranking of countries was observed for the 50% VE scenario (**Table S6**). For all resistance types, vaccine-avertable productivity losses were smaller than vaccine-avertable medical expenditures in a constant ratio of approximately 1:4.

On a per capita basis, the WHO African region displayed the highest avertable monetized DALYs per capita associated with first-line treatment resistance, with a median of \$0.84 (IQR: \$0.50-1.41) (**Figure 3**). The countries with the highest levels of combined vaccine-avertable medical expenditures and

productivity losses per capita associated with first-line treatment resistance were also concentrated in Africa, with Angola, Equatorial Guinea, Botswana, Gabon, and Nigeria ranking among the top seven (**Figure S1**).

For meropenem resistance, the WHO Eastern Mediterranean region had the highest median avertable monetized DALYs per capita at \$0.46 (IQR: 0.24-0.55), followed by the WHO South-East Asia region with a median of \$0.45 (IQR: 0.23-0.71) (**Figure 3**). Six countries in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean region were among the top seven countries associated with the highest medical expenditures and productivity losses per capita: Iran, Pakistan, Yemen, Libya, Djibouti, and Lebanon (**Figure S1**). Maps of the avertable monetized DALYs per capita in each country by resistance type are available in **Figure S2**, and maps of the avertable societal costs per capita in each country by resistance type are available in **Figure S3**.

Medical expenditures associated with neonatal sepsis caused by *K. pneumoniae*

In all income groups, the median direct expenditures associated with a hospital stay are greater than the costs of antibiotics in all scenarios, except among cases in LICs requiring third-line treatment, where the costs of antibiotics are larger than the costs of the hospital stay (**Figure S4A**). The proportional cost of antibiotics in LICs and LMICs is greater than in UMICs. First-line antibiotics cost a median of 2.5 days of income in LICs (IQR: 1.9-2.9), 0.8 days of income (IQR: 0.5-1.2) in LMICs, and 0.4 days of income (IQR: 0.3-0.7) in UMICs (**Figure S4B**). For cases requiring second-line treatment (ceftriaxone), the cumulative costs of antibiotics comprise the equivalent of 17.2 days of income (IQR: 12.4-23.1) in LICs, 5.1 (IQR: 4.2-6.8) in LMICs, and 1.7 (IQR: 1.4-2.5) in UMICs (**Figure S4B**). For cases requiring third-line treatment (meropenem), the cumulative costs of antibiotics comprise the equivalent of 23.9 days of income (IQR: 17.2-30.0) in LICs, 6.9 (IQR: 5.9-8.9) in LMICs, and 2.3 (IQR: 1.8-3.2) in UMICs (**Figure S4B**).

The costs of first-line treatment (including antibiotic costs and hospital stay) for a single case of neonatal sepsis were at levels deemed “catastrophic expenditures” in five countries: Iran, Lebanon, Yemen, Equatorial Guinea, and Argentina. The costs of second-line treatment (including additional antibiotic costs and longer hospital stays due to resistance) were catastrophic in an additional two countries: Afghanistan and Uzbekistan. Under a more stringent definition of catastrophic expenditures as 25% of household income, first-line treatment costs were still catastrophic in four countries: Iran, Lebanon, Yemen, and Argentina, whereas second-line treatment costs were also catastrophic in Equatorial Guinea.

Discussion

To our knowledge, this is the first study modelling the economic impact of a hypothetical maternal vaccine against *K. pneumoniae*, a leading cause of neonatal sepsis in LMICs. Our study shows that a maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine with coverage equivalent to the maternal tetanus vaccine and 70% VE could avert \$6.9 billion (95% CI: 5.6-8.3) in monetized DALYs annually across 107 LMICs. These values represent avertable costs from all—susceptible and resistant—vaccine-avertable cases. Such a vaccine could avert \$2.6 billion (1.7-3.6) in monetized DALYs, \$47.7 million (17.2-102.4) in medical expenditures, and \$12.4 (7.7-18.6) in productivity losses associated with caregiver absenteeism from work associated with meropenem-resistant *K. pneumoniae* annually.

We assessed the potential economic impact using three metrics—medical expenditures, productivity loss, and monetized DALYs—to capture different facets of neonatal sepsis. Monetized DALYs reflect the continued lifelong impact that neonatal sepsis survivors face and capture nonfatal health risks. We found that the lifelong impact reflected in YLDs was greater than from YLLs due to the high prevalence and high disability weights of long-term sequelae from neonatal sepsis (2,31). On the other hand, estimating avertable medical expenditures and productivity losses due to caregiver absenteeism from work give an immediate picture of the societal costs associated with neonatal sepsis. The largest national vaccine-avertable economic burden from vaccination was projected for countries with large populations, such as India, Nigeria, China, and Indonesia. On a per-capita basis, countries displaying the largest vaccine-avertable economic burden were those with the highest GNI per capita.

Similar countries ranked high in the top avertable burden per capita (measured in both monetized DALYs and combined medical expenditures and productivity loss) when considering resistance to first- and second-line treatments. For these two resistance profiles, Angola ranked highest in terms of avertable medical expenditures and productivity loss, while Argentina, Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, Iran, Nigeria, and the Dominican Republic were consistently among the top seven. Botswana, Gabon, and Equatorial Guinea have higher GNI per capita, contributing to their elevated vaccine-avertable costs. However, when examining meropenem resistance, countries in the WHO Eastern Mediterranean region, where meropenem resistance rates are higher, displayed the highest vaccine-avertable burden per capita.

The low estimate for avertable monetized DALYs and avertable societal costs associated with meropenem resistance in the African region is largely due to initial low resistance estimates of 7.0% (95% CrI: 3.2%-12.7%) drawn from the study modelling the vaccine-avertable health burden (10). However, a recent meta-analysis showed that the pooled prevalence of meropenem resistance among *K. pneumoniae* isolates from neonates with sepsis in Africa was 21.9% (95% CI: 9.1-34.8%) (43). Therefore, our calculations likely underestimate the actual impact. Additionally, in the WHO South-East Asia region,

the monetized DALYs associated with meropenem resistance were higher than those associated with ceftazidime resistance, which reflects high rates of meropenem resistance in the region (10).

Our estimates of vaccine-avertable monetized DALYs are contextualized by previous work in estimating the economic burden of neonatal sepsis. Ranjeva and colleagues estimated the annual DALYs caused by neonatal sepsis of any etiology in Sub-Saharan Africa and used a similar approach (VSL-based) to the present study to monetize these outcomes in 2018 (44). Their study estimated an annual neonatal sepsis burden in Sub-Saharan Africa of \$10 billion using the same elasticity value for VSL (44). Our estimate for the vaccine-avertable burden of *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis in the WHO African region was \$1.4 billion (1.1-1.7 billion). While the makeup of countries is different, the comparison contextualizes the scale of our results: considering that *K. pneumoniae* accounts for approximately 25% of neonatal sepsis (45,46), 70% VE scenario, and approximately 85% vaccine coverage (10), our estimate of \$1.4 billion is well within the expected range. With respect to drug-specific resistance patterns, our estimates are conservative, as we propagate conservative prevalence estimates from prior study (10).

Though the costs of medical care were a relatively small proportion of societal costs, an in-depth analysis reveals that LICs and LMICs were disproportionately affected compared to UMICs by the medical costs associated with increased resistance. For infections requiring third-line treatment, the median total cost of antibiotic treatment increases by 9.6, 8.6, and 5.6 times in LICs, LMICs, and UMICs, respectively when compared to first-line treatment. Moreover, the median number of days of income needed to pay for antibiotic treatments is highest in LICs, followed by LMICs, and UMICs, for first-line, second-line, and third-line treatment. To determine whether this ranking may have resulted from applying a single antibiotic price for each region, we repeated the analysis in terms of international \$ by adjusting for PPP separately in each of the 107 countries and found a similar pattern (**Figure S5**). Vaccination can help address these inequities by preventing infections and, therefore, obfuscating the need for antibiotics.

Currently, there are no licensed vaccines against *K. pneumoniae* infections; however, development efforts are advancing through various stages (26,47,48). Recently, a Phase I clinical trial in healthy adults has been evaluating the safety and immunogenicity of a bivalent vaccine (CHO-V08) targeting nosocomial and community-acquired infections caused by hypervirulent K1 and K2 serotypes (ID: NCT07016152) (49). Previously, a Phase I/II clinical trial evaluated the safety and immunogenicity of a tetravalent vaccine (Kleb4V) in adults aged 18 to 55 years (ID: NCT04959344) (50). In addition to these early-phase clinical studies, several collaborative efforts between biotechnology companies and academic institutions are exploring the discovery and preclinical potential of various vaccines against *K. pneumoniae* infections (51–58). Although there is currently no *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine candidate in active clinical trials (26), recent advancements in maternal vaccination are noteworthy. In March 2025, the World Health Organization prequalified a maternal respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) vaccine, highlighting the feasibility

of such vaccines and the importance of their economic evaluation (59). A future extension of this study could involve a cost-effectiveness analysis, which would outline the economic implications of vaccine administration in various countries. These analyses are necessary to assist countries with vaccine prioritization and policy implementation once vaccines receive approval for safety and efficacy.

In addition to reducing infection burden, vaccines have been shown to reduce antimicrobial use (AMU) in countries across the income spectrum (e.g., pneumococcal conjugate and rotavirus vaccination (11), RSV vaccination (60), and seasonal influenza vaccination (61)). By calculating avertable medical expenditures, we provided a framework for quantifying the direct economic benefits of reduced AMU. However, quantifying the indirect benefits of reduced AMU (i.e., reduced selection pressure leading to less rapid AMR development) remains challenging. Shrestha and colleagues previously estimated that the economic cost of increased resistance per antibiotic unit consumed in the US and Thailand ranged from \$0.10 to \$0.70 per antibiotic unit consumed (62).

Our study has several limitations. First, we utilized health burden estimates from a previous study and were constrained by missing data across the 107 countries included in our projections (10). As a result, our calculations reflect a conservative estimate of vaccine-avertable economic burden across these countries. Second, due to a lack of information about specific permutations of multidrug resistance, we could not provide complete estimates of avertable medical expenditures and productivity loss for all cases and instead provided them disaggregated by resistance type. Third, assumptions regarding the input parameters for our model may have contributed to significant uncertainty in our estimates. Although an estimate of OOP medical costs was available for every country in the World Bank database, the actual amounts may vary based on an individual's health insurance scheme, which affected our assessment of catastrophic costs. Additionally, there was a lack of estimates for the distribution of household incomes within countries, which was necessary to calculate catastrophic costs; we used GNI per capita as an average benchmark. Moreover, we did not have comprehensive estimates of drug prices for meropenem or ceftazidime. For the latter, we used ceftriaxone prices as a proxy for the pricing of injectable third-generation cephalosporins. Another potential methodological limitation of this study is that we used regional estimates in US\$ for antibiotic prices and applied the same estimate to all countries within each WHO region. Our estimates are influenced by our choice of VSL elasticity and discount rate; we selected the most appropriate values for this analysis, based on current commonly accepted practices. However, global totals under varying scenarios are provided in **Table S8**. Finally, recent research has suggested that VSL should be calculated differently at the tails of the age distribution, which applies in this study since our focus population was neonates (63).

Our results indicate that a maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine could address disparities associated with the burden of neonatal sepsis in LMICs, by substantially reducing the societal economic burden and

catastrophic health expenditures. Given the increasing resistance to third-line treatments globally, investing in the development of a safe and effective maternal *K. pneumoniae* vaccine should be a priority for international vaccine development efforts. The framework provided in this study could provide regional and country-specific estimates to inform vaccine prioritization decision-making.

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Figures and Tables

Figure 1. Economic impact model conceptual chart. We provide a conceptual chart of our model to evaluate the economic impact of a potential *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine. All economic outputs in this chart (purple) represent avertable values due to vaccination. Epidemiologic model inputs are shown in yellow, other inputs are shown in orange, and health intermediates are shown in magenta. All input values are given in **Table 1** and **Text S1**.
 Abbreviations: OOP = out-of-pocket, YLD = years lived with disability, YLL = years of life lost, DALY = disability-adjusted life years, GNI = gross national income, VSLY = value of a statistical life-year.

Table 1. List of model inputs and parameters.

Input/Parameter	Description	Scale	Distribution/Calculation	Source
Epidemiological inputs				
Avertable cases	Avertable cases of neonatal sepsis due to <i>K. pneumoniae</i> annually under varying scenarios	By country	Gamma distributions derived from published estimates	(10)
Avertable deaths	Avertable deaths from neonatal sepsis due to <i>K. pneumoniae</i> annually under varying scenarios	By country	Gamma distributions derived from published estimates	(10)
Health parameters				
Disability weights	Contribution of neonatal sepsis case towards years of life lived with disability	Same for all countries	Beta distributions estimated from disability weights used in the 2021 GBD study	(31)
Risk of long-term sequelae	Prevalence (%) of long-term sequelae among neonatal sepsis survivors	Same for all countries	Beta distributions estimated from existing meta-analysis	(2)
Life expectancy	Life expectancy at birth, 2021	By country	Ranged uniformly by ± 3 percent	(64)
Length of stay in hospital	Length of stay in the hospital due to neonatal sepsis	Same for all countries	Normal distribution, mean 7.9174 days (standard error = 1.9182) calculated through meta-analysis	(65,66)
Economic parameters				
Antibiotic treatment costs	Cost of empiric antibiotic treatment for neonatal sepsis (US\$)	By region	Point estimates calculated from national surveys and existing literature, ranged uniformly by ± 25 percent	(67,68)
Hospital cost per day	Cost of inpatient hospital day	By country	Gamma distribution derived from published estimates	(38)
Elasticity of VSL (ϵ)	Expected percent change in VSL due to 1% change in income	Same for all countries	$\epsilon = 1.5$, ranged 1.3-1.7 for sensitivity analysis	(32)
% Health expenditures OOP	Percent of health expenditures that are out-of-pocket, 2021	By country	Ranged uniformly by ± 5 percent	(39)
GNI per capita	GNI per capita, 2021 (US\$, Atlas method)	By country	Ranged uniformly by ± 5 percent	(64)
Income per day	Individual income per day, 2021	By country	GNI per capita divided by 365	(64)

This table provides all model inputs and parameters and their sources. Where detailed calculations or meta-analysis were required, further explanation is given in **Text S1**.

Abbreviations: VE = vaccine efficacy, VSL = value of a statistical life, OOP = out-of-pocket, GBD = Global Burden of Disease, GNI = gross national income, GDP = gross national product

Figure 2. Annual avertable monetized DALYs per capita from a *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine by country and geographic region. We illustrate the annual avertable monetized DALYs per capita associated with *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis by A) country and B) geographic region. For A), values reflect the mean of 100,000 simulations by country. For B), values reflect the median of country estimates in each region, and error bars represent the interquartile range for the region. All values are given in 2024 US\$. Abbreviations: AFR = African Region, SEAR = South-East Asia Region, AMR = Region of the Americas, WPR = Western Pacific Region, EMR = Eastern Mediterranean Region, EUR = European Region.

Table 2. Annual estimate of economic burden associated with AMR avertable by a *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine.

Resistance type	Annual vaccine-avertable economic burden, 2024 US\$ (95% CI)		
	Monetized DALYs <i>billions</i>	Medical expenditures <i>millions</i>	Productivity Loss <i>millions</i>
Ampicillin/Gentamicin	4.3 (3.2-5.6)	73.1 (26.6-153.8)	19.2 (12.6-27.4)
Ceftazidime	4.0 (2.8-5.2)	62.0 (22.8-132.9)	15.5 (9.7-23.2)
Meropenem	2.6 (1.7-3.6)	47.7 (17.2-102.4)	12.4 (7.7-18.6)

Values are given in 2024 US\$ along with 95% confidence intervals. Reflects calculations for the baseline scenario, which assumes a vaccination campaign with 70% efficacy and coverage equivalent to the maternal tetanus vaccine. Values are presented as the annual estimate of avertable burdens for 107 countries; see Methods.

Abbreviations: CI = confidence interval, DALYs = disability-adjusted life-years

Figure 3. Annual avertable monetized DALYs per capita by *K. pneumoniae* maternal vaccine by geographic region and resistance type. We illustrate the annual monetized DALYs per capita associated with *K. pneumoniae* neonatal sepsis by geographic region when considering resistance to ampicillin/gentamicin, ceftazidime, and meropenem independently. Diamonds reflect the median of country estimations in each region, and error bars represent the interquartile range. Values are given in 2024 US\$. Abbreviations: DALYs = disability-adjusted life-years, AFR = African Region, SEAR = South-East Asia Region, AMR = Region of the Americas, WPR = Western Pacific Region, EMR = Eastern Mediterranean Region, EUR = European Region.

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